

Influence of Sociability and Religiosity on Moral and Personality Development of Adolescents in Ekiti State University

Ajayi Olubukola Ph.D

*Department of Psychology and Behavioural Studies,
Faculty of Social Sciences, Ekiti State University, Nigeria*

Abstract

The present study investigated the influence of religiosity and sociability on moral and personality development of adolescent. Data were collected by means of structured questionnaire; the study adopted a survey research design which involves 250 participants which were selected through random sampling technique. The findings of this current study reveal that religiosity and sociability did not jointly predict personality development ($F(2, 242) = 2.47$ $p > .05$). Also, religiosity does not independently predict personality development ($\beta = .119$ $t = 1.86$ $p > .05$) and sociability does not independently predict personality development ($\beta = -.063$ $t = -.984$ $p > .05$). The study also reveal that religiosity and sociability did not jointly predict morality development ($F(2, 242) = .347$ $p > .05$). Also, religiosity does not independently predict morality development ($\beta = .016$ $t = p > .05$) and sociability does not independently predict morality development ($\beta = .057$ $t = .820$ $p > .05$). However, the findings of this study were discussed in light of existing literature, conclusion and recommendation were given based on the findings.

Keywords: *Sociability, Religiosity, Moral, Personality Development, Adolescent.*

Suggested citation: Olubukola, A. (2024). Influence of Sociability and Religiosity on Moral and Personality Development of Adolescents in Ekiti State University. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(4), 102-109. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2024.1(4).10

Introduction

Adolescence from the Latin word “adolescere” which means “to grow up”. Adolescent is a unique developmental period during which people experience a pile-up of life changes not previously encountered. This period is marked by the onset of puberty, changing socio-environmental context and tasks (e.g. transition from junior to high school) and the gradual move to more independence and autonomy from parent (Ge, Lorenz, Conger, Elder and Simon, 1994; Spear 2000; Windle, 1992). Adolescent is the vulnerable age group in the society, because growing up as a teenager is usually pretty stressful and exciting at the same time. It is because socially, the adolescents are no more consider a child, yet the adult. In fact, it is considered that adolescent is a time to try new things whether it is about self-identity or about choosing peers (Dodge & Pristein, 2008:63).

Adolescence has further been described as a period during which maturity is attained; a period of transition between childhood and adulthood, a period of transition during which an emotionally immature individual approaches the culmination of his physical and mental growth; a time of “rebirth”.

Morally, adolescence can be evaluated as responsible agent who is not free to choose how to act even when there are urges and internal forces that direct and predispose him/her to act in a particular way. This implicates that external environment reshapes the internal psychics that naturally compel one to act in a particular way and this external environment may include societal rules, moral, beliefs, norms, societal regulations, family rules, religious beliefs, law etc.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Also, in Kohlberg's 1963 moral development he defines it as a time of conventional morality characterized by an acceptance of societal conclusions concerning rights and wrong. It is the concept of an individual with inner thoughts and feelings controlling his or her actions, a transitional period between physical and psychological development between childhood and maturity (Johnson & Johnson, 2004).

According to Allport (1961) personality refer to distinctive pattern of behaviour, mannerism, thought, motives, and emotion that characterize an individual overtime and across different situation. Adolescents tend towards the attainment of complete ethical personality through release from predominantly egoistic motivation of life. This involve at once increase self-guidance yet a deeper sense of obligation, a heighten individualism into social-realization (Gross, 2010).

Religion is believed to be another important factor that shapes and influence ones' morality and personality development. The existence of faith and spirituality in the meta-moral characteristics of the complete moral person suggests that religion and morality may be related and that religion may promote the realization of the moral person (Adebayo, 2007). Rules about how life should be live which are not restricted to the family alone but also to the social dimension. The norms and rules prevent individuals from misconduct within the society (thou shall not kill, not commit adultery, not steal, and not bear false witness against thy neighbour.... The ten commandment) and therefore have effect on moral and personality development of an individual. In the world there exists different religion such as Christianity, Muslim, Buddhism, Hinduism Judaism.

Sociability during adolescent involves a dramatic change in the quantity and quality of social relationship, consequently, according to Jean Piaget developmental psychologist who posited younger children will often use the word friend to refer any other children whom they happen to known, however as the children become adolescent they begin to differentiate friend's from acquaintance indicating a more mature understanding of the qualitatively different ways to another person.

Sociability is a central to critical period during adolescent period, because adolescent can easily be influenced by the people which they develop close relationships with. Relationships are vital in the sociability of an adolescent in other to maintain and sustained relationship with classmates, schoolmates and colleagues at work as well as to establish intimate relationship with close friend, future partner and member of the family. Individual who lack the skills of interacting appropriately with others are said to be unsociable, aggressive, bashful or isolated. On the other hand, social isolation among peer-rejected teens has been linked to a variety of negative behaviour, such as delinquency (Kupersmidt & Coie, 1990).

In addition, adults who had interpersonal problems during adolescence appear to be at much greater risk for psychosocial difficulties during adulthood (Hansen et al., 1995). During this time, involvement with the peer group tends to be most intense, and conformity and concerns about acceptance are at their peak. The intense desire to belong to a particular group can influence young adolescents to go along with activities in which they would otherwise not engage (Muccucci, 1998; Santrock, 2001).

Materials and Methods

Research Design

Research design adopted was an ex-post facto field research design. It was adopted because the researcher did not manipulate independent variables in the study.

Participants

This study was carried out in Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, whereby two hundred and fifty questionnaires were used. Copies of questionnaires were distributed to the research participants to measure their response.

Variables

The independent variables involved in the study are sociability and religiosity, while the dependent variables are personality and morality development.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Random sampling technique was used to draw undergraduate students of Ekiti State University.

Measures

Questionnaire comprising of four sections was used for this study, sex and age were contained in the section A which was used to gather personal information about the participants. Section B consists of Big Five Inventory (BFI), section C consist of Sociability Questionnaire, section D consists of Religiosity Scale (RS) and section E consists of Moral Development Scale for Professionals.

Religiosity Scale (RS)

A reversed version of Poppleton and Pilkington (1963) religious attitude scale was used to measure religiosity. In its original form, the scale contained twenty one items and was primarily developed for a Christian population. The bid to have equivalent measure of religiosity for Muslim and Christian research participant led to its revision for the purpose of the proposed study. In reversing the scale, five items (item no 2, 3, 10, 12 and 18) were reworded to take care of Muslim research participant for example, item no 2 read “Jesus was an important and interesting historical figure in no divine way was reworded to read Jesus Christ/Mohammed was an important and interesting historical figure but in no divine way”. Also, item no 12, which its original version read “the more scientific discoveries are made the more the glory of God be revealed” was reworded with the more scientific discoveries are made, the more the glory to God/Allah is revealed. Similarly item no 18, which its original version read “parents have a duty to teach elementary Christian truth to their children was reworded to read parents have a duty to teach elementary Christian/Islamic truth to their children.

However, item 7, 9 and 14 its original version was not included in the reverse version because of the absence of their equivalents in Islamic faith. For example, item 7 read” the miracle recorded in the bible really happened”. Item 9 read “Christ atoned for our sins by sacrifice on the cross”.

Reliability

Poppleton and Pilkington (1963) reported a reliability coefficient alpha of .97 for the original version thus suggesting a strong reliability of the scale to test the reliability of the reversed version, the scale was administered in a pilot study on a sample of 50 Christians and 50 Muslims drawn from the adult population of MBA part time student of the university of Ado-Ekiti. The split half reliability coefficient of the Christian and Muslim sample were .75 and .97, respectively.

Validity

Poppleton and Pilkington did a discriminant validity of the original religious attitude scale have found it to be very strong in discriminating significantly between pro and anti-religious people. To test the validity of the reversed version a pilot study earlier reported was carried out. Christian will set participant were made to respond to the reverse attitude scale, the original scale and Francis’ (1978) attitude towards Christianity scale, while the Muslim sample were made to respond to the reverse religious attitude scale and Wilde and Joseph’s(1997) attitude towards Islam scale correlating scores obtained from the revised religious attitude scale with Francis’ attitude towards Christianity yielded a concurrent validity coefficient of .88:with scores obtained from the original version, concurrent validity coefficient was .95 while with Wilde and Joseph’s attitude towards Islam was .89($P < .01, n = 50$).

Scoring

In scoring a religious attitude scale the Likert five points was used. Positively worded items were scored directly; strongly agree being 5, agree being 4, undecided being 3, disagree being 2, strongly disagree being 1. Negatively worded items were scored in reverse order. A respondent’s level of religiosity was derived

from the aggregate of his/her scores on the 18 items of the scale. For the entire sample of 745 for the present study the mean scores standard deviation and median were 70, 11.02 and 71 respectively. Research participant whose scores fell below the median were categorized as low in religiosity while those whose scores fell within the median or above it was categorized as high in religiosity.

Big Five Personality Inventory (BFI)

The big five personality traits are the best accepted and most commonly used model of personality in academic psychology. The BFI scale measuring the Big Five personality traits Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, and Openness. The Big Five model is the most scientifically sound way of classifying personality differences and is the most widely used among research psychologists. The big five come from the statistical study of responses to personality items.

Validity Test

Upon receiving all the responses in the survey, factor analysis was conducted for the Big Five personality traits scale. Prior to conduct factor analysis, inspection of the correlation matrix was done and it indicated that most of the item coefficients were 0.3 and above. The analysis of Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Partial Correlations showed that the value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin for measuring of sampling adequacy (KMO/MSA) was 0.806. It exceeds the minimum value of 0.6 for a great factor analysis (0.8 – 0.9). Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant at $p < 0.001$ where it supported the factorability of the correlation matrix. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) extracted four factors compared to the original of five factors after cross loadings were deleted and loadings below 0.35 were discarded. These 4 factors cumulatively captured 48.572% of the variance. Factor 1, 2, 3 and 4 contributed 20.178%, 11.589%, 9.638% and 7.167% of the common variance with Eigen values of 4.237, 2.434, 2.024 and 1.505 respectively. The factor loading values for the scales were in the range of 0.573 to 0.803. Drawing upon the factor analysis results, items that loaded on Factor 1 (7 items) were labeled as openness to experience, Factor 2 (5 items) were categorized as extraversion, Factor 3 (5 items) were named as neuroticism and Factor 4 (4 items) were designated as conscientiousness.

Reliability of the Scale

The reliability test results show that the reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) for each factor of the personality traits was 0.779 (openness to experience), 0.727 (conscientiousness), 0.725 (extraversion) and 0.716 (neuroticism). Since all the reliability coefficients have surpassed the minimum value of 0.7, the measures were deemed consistent and reliable throughout the study.

Scoring

BFI scale scoring ("R" denotes reverse-scored items):

Extraversion: 1, 6R, 11, 16, 21R, 26, 31R, 36

Agreeableness: 2R, 7, 12R, 17, 22, 27R, 32, 37R, 42

Conscientiousness: 3, 8R, 13, 18R, 23R, 28, 33, 38, 43R

Neuroticism: 4, 9R, 14, 19, 24R, 29, 34R, 39

Openness: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35R, 40, 41R, 44

Moral Development Scale for Professionals (MDSP)

The MDSP is based on Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of moral development, which proposes that individuals pass through moral stages from the concrete to the abstract. The scale has been developed with the aim of measuring moral development among adults, who can be expected to have reached the upper levels of Kohlberg's stages of moral development, i.e, the conventional and post conventional levels. The summated self-report instrument was developed in the Norwegian language in Norway. Thirty-two items reflecting the 4 stages of moral development at the conventional and post conventional levels, 8 items for each stage, were formulated in a Likert-type format. After different actions to test the

appropriateness of the items, an instrument with 12 items was finally chosen to be suitable to have in the instrument.

Reliability assessed as internal consistency with the Cronbach's alpha coefficient reached a value of 0.67 in the study group of 326 students. Since a value of 0.70 is considered to be sufficient for group level comparisons, the reliability of MDSP should be considered as acceptable in the initial testing and development procedures.

The instrument has 12 Likert-type items ranging from 1 ("not agree at all") to 5 ("agree completely"), which yields a total sum between 12 and 60. A higher score indicates a higher degree of moral development. The intention of MDSP has been to provide a scale that can be used to evaluate moral development among, for example, students and professionals for whom it is essential to have a well-developed ability for moral behavior, ethical thinking, and decision making. Validity was also partly supported by a factor analysis that explained 51% of the variances with a logical 4-factor solution.

Sociability Questionnaire

Sociability questionnaire is a 7-item questionnaire developed by Hanewicz and Bellamy (1988). All the items are scored directly and attracts 1-5 rating thereby making the scores to range from 7 to 35 with a mean 26.2. Hanewicz and Bellamy (1998), this was translated to Arabic, and the alpha reliability of this dual language version was 0.72.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher politely approached the participants in Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. However, 200 participants were selected through random sampling method. The participants were assured that their participation is voluntary and they can discontinue their participation at any point in time. However, the researcher verbally explained to the participants who do not understand some items and how to fill them. Some participants were debriefed about the nature of the study upon completion of the questionnaire. At the end of the retrieval, only 246 questionnaires were useful. The other 4 were improperly filled and were discarded.

Method of Data Analyses

The score obtained was analysed using the statistical method well known and commonly use in psychological research. Regression method of data analysis was adopted to test the various hypotheses.

Results

Table 1. Regression Summary Table Showing the Joint and Independent Predictive Influence of Religiosity and Sociability on Personality Development

DV	IVC	β	t	R ²	df	F
Personality Development	Religiosity	.119	1.86 ^{ns}	.020	242	2.47 ^{ns}
	Sociability	-.063	-.984 ^{ns}			

Note: ns=p>.05

Table 1 indicated that Religiosity and Sociability does not jointly predict Personality Development (F (2, 242) = 2.47 p>.05). Also, Religiosity does not independently predict Personality Development (β = .119 t= 1.86 p>.05) and Sociability does not independently predict Personality Development (β = -.063 t= -.984 p>.05).

Table 2. Regression Summary Table Showing the Joint and Independent Predictive Influence of Religiosity and Sociability on Moral Development

DV	IVC	β	t	R ²	df	F
Personality Development	Religiosity	.016	.241 ^{ns}		2	
				.003	242	.347 ^{ns}
	Sociability	.057	.820 ^{ns}			

Note: ns=p>.05

Table 2 indicated that Religiosity and Sociability does not jointly predict Morality Development (F (2, 242) = .347 p>.05). Also, Religiosity does not independently predict Morality Development (β = .016 t=.241^{ns} p>.05) and Sociability does not independently predict Morality Development (β = .057 t= .820^{ns} p>.05).

Discussion

The results of this findings shows that there is no significant influence of religiosity on Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Neuroticism, however, the findings agree with Brown (1962) who reported a no significant correlation between neuroticism and religious beliefs, Siegman (1963) reported significant correlation between religiosity and extraversion in a population of Protestants and religiosity and introversion in a population of Jews. Inconsistency in relationship between religion and personality could also be observed in findings of studies that investigated the influence of religion on personality and adjustment. Brown (1962) and Francis (1992) explained that lack of relationship observed between Extraversion and religiosity is an indication that Extraversion is not fundamental to social conditioning and tenderness.

A significant influence of religiosity was found not on moral development. Weak social bonds and weak bonds to religion, institutions, or other people may make a person more susceptible to act defiantly due to the belief that there is no one or nothing to whom or which to answer. Engaging in deviant acts further weaken already compromised social bonds. It weakens a person's belief in morality, decreases attachments to other people, and reduces commitments (Matsueda, 1989).

This current findings result agrees with Erie (2001) who reported that religiosity is not a good predictor of moral reasoning. High religious adolescents are not likely rule-oriented than low religious people. According to this study, High religious people may not likely give more consideration to nature and consequently therefore acts in judging right and wrong more than low religious people, this suggest that high religious people are likely not cognitively complex in moral reasoning. Feder (1984) also argued against the supposedly conventional morality of the rule-oriented reasoning of religious people.

Hypothesis three result shows that there is no significant influence of sociability on personality. This current finding is against Papalia, old and Fedman (2004) who reported that some adolescents are of course more sociable than others, reflecting such temperament trait as their usual mood, readiness to accept new people and ability to adapt to change. Sociability help to elicit impact seeking behavior, open to experience, freedom and trust in one's ability rather remain complacent in one's subservient and subsistence world. Roger (1961).

Hypothesis four result shows that there is no significant influence of sociability on moral development, this study is against findings which was provided by Bandura and McDonald's (1963) who observed that children exposed to an adult moral model who made mature moral judgment were more likely to give more mature moral responses than children who were not exposed. Also Kohlberg 1963 sees morality as an acceptance of societal conclusions concerning rightness and wrongness, consequent upon this, it requires the individual to interact with the society and this can be achieved through sociability.

There is no significant joint influence of sociability and religiosity on Extraversion, Conscientiousness, Openness, Agreeableness and Neuroticism. This is against one study that has corroborated Eysenck's

(1967) in Heaven (1992). Heaven investigated the relationship between Eysenckian personality dimensions and the social attitudes of 273 adult Australians. The social attitudes investigated were hedonism, religion and morality. Analysis of data revealed a significant positive relationship between extraversion and hedonism and religion/morality.

Hypothesis seven shows that there is no significant joint influence of sociability and religiosity on morality development and personality development.

Conclusion

In the light of the results of these findings and discussions, it is plausible to conclude thus; there is no significant influence of religiosity on personality development; there is no significant influence of religiosity on moral development; there is no significant influence of sociability on personality development, there is no significant influence of sociability on moral development; there is no significant joint influence of religiosity and sociability on personality development, there is no significant joint influence of religiosity and sociability on morality development; there is no significant joint influence of religiosity and sociability on morality development and personality development.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, family should also create a better environment for adolescents being a first agent of socialization and moral institutions and positive social group that engender and foster a moratorium exploration of adolescent creativity and socialism rather than group that subjected adolescent to egoistic egocentrism. Political and religious leaders should also formulate a policy that encourage religion activities so as build national development. Further researches could also check ethnicity and increase the size number so as to generate the result to a larger population.

References

- Allport, G.W. (1961). *Pattern and growth in personality*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Bandura, A. & McDonald, F.J. (1963). Influence of social reinforcement and the behavior of models in shaping children's moral judgment. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, (3), 274-381. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0044714>
- Brown, L. B. (1962). A study of religious belief. *British Journal of Psychology*, 53(3), 259-272. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.1962.tb00832.x>
- Dodge, K. A. & Prinstein, M. J. (2008). *Understanding peer influence in children and adolescents*. Guilford Press.
- Eysenck, H. J. (1967). *The biological basis of personality*. Springfield, Illinois: Charles C. Thomas.
- Feder, A. (1984). Kohlberg's theory and the religious Jew. *Religious Education*, 79(2), 163-182.
- Francis, L. J. (1978). Attitude and longitude: A study in measurement. *Character Potential*, 8, 119 – 130 .
- Francis, L. J. (1992). Is psychoticism really a dimension of personality fundamental to religiosity?. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 13(6), 645-652.
- Francis, L.J. (1993). The personality characteristics of student church goers. *Personality and individual differences*, 15(4), 373-380. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(93\)90064-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(93)90064-A)
- Ge, X., Lorenz, F. O., Conger, R. D., Elder, G. H., & Simons, R. L. (1994). Trajectories of stressful life events and depressive symptoms during adolescence. *Developmental Psychology*, 30(4), 467-483. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.30.4.467>
- Gross, J. J. (2010). The future's so bright, I gotta wear shades. *Emotion review*, 2(3), 212-216.

- Hansen, D. J., Giacoletti, A. M., & Nangle, D. W. (1995). *Social interactions and adjustment*. In V. B. Van Hasselt & M. Hersen (Eds.), *Handbook of adolescent psychopathology: A guide to diagnosis and treatment*. New York: Lexington Books.
- Heaven, P. (1992). *Social and economic beliefs in adulthood*. In P.C.L. Heaven (Ed), *Life-Span Development*. Sydney: *Harcourt Brace Jovanovich*, 242-264.
- Kohlberg, L. (1963). The development of children's orientation toward a moral order, 1. *Sequence in the development of moral thought Vita Humanan*, 6, 11-33. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000269667>
- Kohlberg, L. (2008). The Development of Children's Orientations Toward a Moral Order. *Human development*, 51(1), 8-20.
- Kupersmidt, J. B., & Coie, J. D. (1990). Preadolescent peer status, aggression, and school adjustment as predictors of externalizing problems in adolescence. *Child Development*, 61, 1350- 1363. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.1990.tb02866.x>
- Matsueda, R. L. (1989). The dynamics of moral beliefs and minor deviance. *Social Forces*, 68(2), 428-457.
- Micucci, J. A. (1998). *The adolescent in family therapy: Breaking the cycle of conflict and control*. New York: Guilford.
- Poppleton, P., & Pilkington, G. (1963). The measurement of religious attitudes in a university population. *British Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 2, 20-36.
- Rogers, C. R. (1961). *On becoming a person*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin .
- Santrock, J.W. (2011). *Adolescence*. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Siegmán (1963) reported significant correlation between religiosity and extraversion in a population
- Siegmán, A.W. (1963). A cross- cultural investigation of the relationship between introversion, social attitudes and social behavior. *British Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 2, 196-208. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8260.1970.tb00667.x>
- Spear, L. P. (2000). Neurobehavioral changes in adolescence. *Current directions in psychological science*, 9(4), 111-114.
- Wild, A. & Joseph S. (1997). Religiosity and Personality in a Moslem Context. *Personality and Individual Difference*, 23, 899-900. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(97\)00098-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(97)00098-6)
- Windle, M. (1992). Temperament and social support in adolescence: Interrelations with depressive symptoms and delinquent behaviors. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 21(1), 1-21.

